

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE ACTIVITIES IN DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS OF ESP STUDENTS BY PRESENTATION, PRACTICE AND PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

This article reveals the role of interactive activities in the teaching of a foreign language. The author of the article believes that the importance of learning a foreign language is undisputed. But there are a lot of problems in the process of learning a foreign language. These include the problem of increasing the effectiveness of oral language learning in foreign language lessons, which is directly related to the gap between theory and practice and the passive nature of learning activities, while the absolute value of society becomes an educated active person capable of continuous self-education, self-development and self-improvement. If modern pedagogical technologies are used in the process of teaching foreign-speaking speech, it will increase the efficiency of teaching this type of speech activity. In order to facilitate the communication of students, we should take into account the specific features of this type of speech activity, such as motivation, purposefulness, activity, connection with the personality and thinking activity of a person, independence, pace and situations. If there are goals and motives of communication, taking into account the specific features of the participants of communication, their age, level of development, etc., then the act of communication will certainly take place within the framework of any speech situation.

Keywords: situation, communication, age, students, level of development, independence, participants of communication, speech, activity, efficiency, modern technology.

АННОТАЦИЯ

данная статья раскрывает роль интерактивных видов деятельности в преподавании иностранного языка. Автор статьи считает, что значение изучения иностранного языка бесспорно. Но при обучении возникает множество проблем. К ним относятся проблема повышения эффективности обучения устной речи на уроках иностранного языка, которая непосредственно связана с разрывом между теорией и практикой и пассивным характером учебной деятельности, тогда как

абсолютной ценностью общества становится образованная активная личность, способная к непрерывному самообразованию, саморазвитию и самосовершенствованию. Если в процессе обучения иноязычной устной речи использовать современные педагогические технологии, то это позволит повысить эффективность обучения данному виду речевой деятельности. Чтобы способствовать общению студентов, мы должны учитывать специфические признаки данного вида речевой деятельности, такие как мотивированность, целенаправленность, активность, связь с личностью и мыслительной деятельностью человека, самостоятельность, темп и ситуативность. Если есть цели и мотивы общения, учтены характерные особенности участников общения, их возраст, уровень развития и т.д., то акт общения, безусловно, состоится в рамках какой-либо речевой ситуации.

Ключевые слова: ситуация, общение, возраст, студенты, уровень развития, самостоятельность, участники общения, речь, деятельность, эффективность, современные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

PPP is a deductive approach to learning. Surely, it was used by almost every teacher in his practice. The approach is universal, does not require shamanic tambourine, unicorn tears, wise knowledge and preparation. First of all the approach is simple and logical - thanks to this it naturally fits into the learning process There is nothing to even talk about, the name shouts for itself. Each person is responsible for its own phase: Presentation, Practice and Production. And furthermore there some steps. The most important part of the lesson is that here the teacher will have to sweat a lot to clearly convey the essence of the lesson topic. It looks like this: the teacher sets the situation using history, video, audio, dialogue, a paragraph from the text - everything where you can find the structure you want to teach. We need a context that will reveal the function and meaning of the new topic in full. It can be either a new time in grammar or a separate structure. For example, for used to you can find a small video about life earlier and now, or just show your photos 5 years ago and recent (students like to learn different details of the life of their teachers. Sometimes I think they work for intelligence...) For instance, women used to wear long dresses. Now they can wear shorts and t-shirts. Women used to wear parasols in the sun. Now they prefer to wearing sunglasses, etc. It is very important that the information is presented in as much detail as possible and used by a direct value. Avoid exclusions to avoid confusing students for starters. Next, accordingly the teacher gives his examples with the structure studied so that students can see how to create and use it on their own. As a result, to make sure that the topic has “entered”, you need to set a couple of concept checking questions.

The drilling stage, where you have to be the notorious “parrot” and repeat the new structure for students, ask them to repeat it together or one at a time until they reach the ideal. There are many exercises for honing a skill at this stage - gap fill exercises, split sentences and matching sentences to pictures.

The main condition here is the complete control of students, their pronunciation, the use of grammar and the eradication of any errors. Timing can vary - it is worth spending as much time on this as it takes your students to understand and assimilate a new topic.

Analyses. Continuing the used to theme, you can give several photos from your life or the life of the character, sketch descriptions with the construction and ask students to correlate the sentences with the photo. Now you can drink a cup of tea and look through Instagram while the students work. LOL. At this stage, the role of the teacher is minimized, but do not lose vigilance. The essence of the Production stage comes down to encouraging weak minds and half-empty vessels to reproduce the new structure on their own in a natural situation. These can be information gaps, a role play, a communication task and my favorite board games on a variety of topics (it’s time to get dusty snakes & ladders).

In order to complete the practice used to, challenge students like throwback thursday, where they need to post an old photo and describe their lives using a new construction.

This is the stage of free practice - here you throw students into the grammar pool, where they need to stay afloat, using everything that you chewed on them before.

During the students’ exercises, write down their mistakes so that at the end they can give out a reasonable feedback, and the lesson did not go to waste.

To begin introducing stress in English lessons, define typical stressed and unstressed patterns. You must also describe how a stressed syllable differs from an unstressed syllable in terms of speech patterns. First of all, the focus of the meaning we are trying to convey lies in the emphasized syllables. Compared to unstressed syllables, they are louder and longer. Usually, emphasis is placed on the syllables of content words, which make up the majority of a sentence. Nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs are the four different categories of words. Unstressed syllables are typically used in structure words, or the smaller words in sentences. Conjunctions, pronouns, articles, and prepositions are a few examples of them. Starting with simple phrases and progressing to more complex ones and dialogs makes this point clear.

As the level of stress changes, demonstrate to the pupil how the intonation or pitch changes. Discuss the various ways stress impacts meaning once students have a good grasp of the idea of emphasizing particular words in sentences. Changing the emphasis of each word in one or two sentences each day to vary their meaning can be incredibly

thrilling. You can mix this with any grammar point you're working on. In an adjective lesson, for instance, you might utilize stress examples to demonstrate emphasis, contrast, or contradiction. Adverbs can help you emphasize your remarks. Consider the following claim:

In an adjective lesson, for instance, you might utilize stress examples to demonstrate emphasis, contrast, or contradiction. Adverbs can help you emphasize your remarks. Consider the following claim:

I want a brand-new, brilliant-blue car. The meaning can vary depending on which word is emphasized the most. As they practice adjusting the emphasis between words, students should think about how the meaning alters. Jazz chants are another helpful tool for training tension, as are having children clap, stomp, or bang to show where the stress is. However, even adults will enjoy stomping or cheering their way to a better understanding. Younger children will profit from this the most.

Reduction and Rhythm.

Inability to understand native speakers is one of the most frequent issues faced by English language learners, with frequent complaints that Americans speak too quickly. Reduction is one of the most significant challenges in this scenario. Students must practice pronunciation that incorporates reduction in order to become proficient. The use of shortened words or sentences in speaking is known as reduction. When natural speakers omit or combine sounds, this occurs. Every English dialect and accent contains frequent instances of this. The following are some examples of reduction: Gimme that instead of give me that,

I dunno instead of I don't know gotta instead of got to (which is a reduction of have to), wanna instead of want to or would like to and the ever common shoulda, coulda, woulda for should have, could have or would have.

Students need to learn to spot declines in their hearing so they don't ruin their fluency. It is true that native speakers occasionally misuse words in their speech, and anyone learning English needs to be aware of the relationship between rhythm and stress. You may allow another instructor to use your classroom to practice rhythm and reduction. After that, the two of you might act in some role plays for the class. Put a focus on cuts, and give them specific objectives for each conversation. You could ask them to select the role-core play's idea, or you could ask them to record any reductions they hear and then define them. The same objectives can be met by using listening activities like group discussions.

The Effects of Intonation on Meaning.

The tiny variation in a language's pattern of stress is referred to as its "intone". Using the improper tone can lead to misunderstandings and even changes in sentence or word meaning. Introduce the basic syntax and intonation of English phrases first.

Statements, yes-or-no questions, and wh-questions are good places to start. Tag questions are another well-liked technique for honing intonation because you can truly emphasize the meaning shifts with varied intonations. Draw arrows on the board to show the direction of the pitch for intonation.

One of the main factors to develop the students speech is elicitation. It is a method that has been effective in getting kids to talk and arouse their attention. Teachers' duties include encouraging students to speak up. When asking a question or providing more instructions, the teacher suggested getting a response from the class. Elicitation is a strategy for encouraging participation from the class. According to experts, elicitation enables teachers to introduce speaking components to kids by seamlessly incorporating speaking abilities into interactive conversations in which the teacher asks questions, the students respond, and the teacher evaluates and corrects their answers. The elicitation technique can help to create a learning environment that is centered on them by allowing students to talk more in class rather than just listening to the teacher's explanation. Elicitation can also be used to test pupils' language proficiency and educate them about unexpected subjects. Effective elicitation gives pupils a setting in which to convey new language and improves their capacity to retain it in the right context. Eliciting assists the teacher in allowing the students to express what they know, which is substantially better than simply providing the class with information. The majority of elicitation methods are already used by English teachers, who use a wide variety of them. On the other hand, the researcher has based her investigation on the numerous elicitation techniques that Tsui has provided (1995). He divides elicitation techniques into the six types that are depicted below.

1. Elicit: inform. The first type of elicitation involves asking students for information. It could come in the shape of WH queries, yes-or-no inquiry, deceptive questions, or a variety of other questions. If the text is a recount, for instance, ask the students about their trip to a stunning location or give them a test on the most recent topic.

2. Elicit: confirm. The students are asked to agree with the instructors' premises in the second sort of elicitation. To determine, for example, how well the students had assimilated the material Declarative, negative polar, and tag interrogative questions are a few examples of question kinds. "Do you understand," or "Is it all right?" are two outstanding examples.

3. Elicit: agree. The third sort of elicitation involves students agreeing with the teacher's presumption that the expression is correct by default. The tag question is one type of inquiry that might be applied. You are aware that low is the polar opposite of high, the teacher replies.

4. Elicit: commit. This sort of elicitation, which is distinct from the others, is the fourth kind. The students are expected to provide more than just a vocal response in response to this elicitation; they are also expected to pledge to take action. Yes/no questions and WH interrogative questions are the two types of questions that can be employed. Encourage students, for instance, to pledge that they will speak English with the English teacher outside of class whenever possible.

5. Elicit: repeat. The repetition of the prior statement is a component of prospective elicitation, the fifth type of elicitation. Either the instructor cannot hear it, or the instructor only requests that the pupils speak the words and sentences clearly. It is possible to ask a "WH question" or "sorry, could you repeat that" instead. or "huh?"

6. Elicit: clarify. In order for students to be aware of their errors, the sixth form of elicitation encourages them to elaborate on earlier statements that were inaccurate. It can take the form of WH interrogatives or high-pitched repetitions of a word or phrase from the previous utterance.

Elicitation works well to involve students in the teaching and learning process. The teacher uses elicitation strategies to elicit replies from the pupils. Elicitation is a method where students are given questions that have been deliberately prepared to rationally target vocabulary or grammar ideas while omitting the forms being taught.

In conclusion, interactive methods are a useful and fruitful component in teaching a foreign language, due to their inherent advantages in developing communicative, cognitive, creative abilities of students, and also due to the possibility to form students' continual interest in the foreign language culture of the country under consideration. Both the teacher and the students gain from well-organized lesson planning. When lesson plans are well-organized and sequential, the classroom operates more smoothly; interruptions are decreased, teacher stress is decreased, and the learning environment for the students is at its best. The lesson plan is a guide for what the class will learn and how it will be accomplished successfully. Following that, you can create applicable learning activities and techniques for getting feedback on students' progress.

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